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ABSTRACT

We present an active alignment and stabilization control system for laser setups based on a thin-disk regenerative amplifier. This method eliminates power and pointing instability during the warm-up period and improves long-term stability throughout the entire operation. The alignment method is based on a four-mirror control system consisting of two motorized mirrors placed within the regenerative amplifier cavity, two additional motorized mirrors external to the amplifier cavity, and four camera detectors. The implemented stabilization system achieves significant performance improvements, increasing the power stability from 1.87% to 0.79% RMS and the peak-to-peak stability from 7.43% to 3.88%. Furthermore, the system significantly enhances beam positional stability, achieving up to a sixfold improvement in certain sensor measurements. The advantage of this method is the removal of long-term pointing instability by adding a second controlled motorized mirror to the cavity, in addition to using only one cavity end mirror for optimizing the overlap with the pump spot on the cavity medium. To achieve higher precision in pointing, the nonlinear hysteresis effect of the piezoelectric actuator is mitigated. Although the power and pointing stability of the cavity are secured, pointing instability at the input of the compressor occurs. This issue is resolved by two additional controlled motorized mirrors external to the cavity.

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I. INTRODUCTION

At the outset, it is important to clarify the concept of stability, which is understood differently in the field of control systems compared to the field of lasers.

In control systems, stability refers to the dynamic behavior of a system, including its ability to respond to various external or internal disturbances and subsequently return to its equilibrium state. In contrast, in the context of solid-state high-power lasers, stability focuses on the device's ability to maintain consistent properties and performance during operation. This includes aspects like beam pointing stability and energy stability, which are crucial for ensuring reliable and precise functioning in various practical applications of high-power lasers, especially in fields in industry like micro-machining or lithography. Misalignment can lead to temporal variations in output power or pulse width in ultrashort laser systems and may cause unpredictable distortion of experimental process and data.

Various systems have been reported since 1988, starting with analog control¹ and digital feedback systems² both based on quadrupole photodiodes, which are not sensitive to the details of the intensity distribution and, therefore, are not able to provide a direct measurement of the beam center. This disadvantage was addressed and removed by using a CCD camera.³ Active cavity optimization using overlap between cavity mode and pump spot based on one mirror feedback loop was reported in 2017.⁴

The active alignment system presented here was developed in the R&D center HiLASE (High average power pulsed LASERs). Center focuses on the development of advanced high-repetition rate, diode-pumped solid state laser (DPSSL) systems. In-house developed laser beamlines have energies ranging from mJ to 100 J and repetition rates ranging from 10 Hz to 1 MHz. One of the major concepts within HiLASE being explored is thin-disk laser amplifiers aiming for 1 ps pulse width at repetition rates between 1 and 100 kHz called the “Perla” platform, which is important for the majority of industrial laser applications, including lithography. Development

of this ultrashort pulsed laser platform has been reported since 2015.^{5,6}

The active alignment control system was developed for this platform to ensure robust and maintenance-free operation of the laser throughout the day. The system automatically eliminates the misalignment of the laser cavity, which results in power instability and a decrease in the output power of the regenerative amplifier. By implementing two additional actively controlled motorized mirrors outside the cavity, the residual pointing error is reduced, ensuring proper input to the compressor.

II. SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

A schematic of the Perla laser system is shown in Fig. 1. It is a home-built thin-disk amplifier operating at 1030 nm wavelength, high repetition rate (51 kHz), and 1 ps ultrashort pulse length after compression, currently setup for 31 W of average power. The laser is placed in a massive aluminum enclosure with temperature-controlled breadboard. Even though the breadboard temperature is stable and, therefore, resistant to changes in external temperature, it is not possible to completely eliminate the power and pointing instability. One reason for this could be the heating of system components by the laser light itself.

Two camera sensors, CAM1 and CAM2, and two motorized mirrors, MM1 and MM2, are placed in the regenerative amplifier cavity. CAM1 monitors the thin disk utilizing a novel method of energy stabilization.⁴ First, a calibration image of the unseeded pump spot must be taken. After the amplifier is seeded, the overlap of the pump spot and amplified pulse is visible as a darker region. Subtraction of this image from the calibration image enables the centroid calculation of the cavity mode position. The motorized mirror MM2 then ensures the overlap with the pump spot on the cavity medium monitored by camera CAM1. In addition to this method,

a second camera, CAM2, is placed behind the cavity end mirror (CEM) to calculate the position of the beam centroid. The motorized mirror MM1 aligns the beam on camera CAM2 to ensure a long-term correct cavity alignment. This control system is referred to as the Cavity Stabilization System (CSS).

Moreover, two motorized mirrors, MM3 and MM4, are placed external to the amplifier cavity. Mirror MM3 aligns the beam to the near-field camera CAM3 using a fractional beam of the polarizing beam splitter (PBS). Mirror MM4 aligns the beam to the far-field camera CAM4. CAM3 is placed as close as possible to the PBS in order to reduce the influence of the MM4's movement. This part of the alignment system is designated as the Beam Stabilization System (BSS).

To measure the beam centroid, the cameras employ a method that involves capturing an image of the laser beam profile and processing it to find the center of mass of the intensity profiles. The process includes filtering the image to reduce noise, applying a centroid algorithm to determine the center of mass, and continuously monitoring this position to ensure precise alignment. This technique is crucial for maintaining the stability and performance of the laser system by providing real-time feedback to the motorized mirrors for necessary adjustments. Detailed procedures for beam centroid measurement can be found in related literature.³

The control system is using TwinCAT 3 PC-based technology. The system comprises two independent PLCs (programmable logic controllers) running under TwinCAT 3.1 Real-Time, which allows CPU cores to be isolated from the guest operating system and offers multi-core support. This guarantees that the processing results are available within a specified period of time and allows computationally intensive tasks, such as camera image processing, to run on different cores. The control system scheme is depicted in Fig. 2. The camera images are processed by the first PLC using TwinCAT 3 Vision, which is integrated into the development platform

FIG. 1. Perla laser system schematic containing four motorized mirrors (MMs) for pointing and power stabilization control system. TDLH—thin disk laser head, OSC—fiber oscillator, PreAMP—fiber preamplifier, PBS—polarizing beam splitter, TFP—thin film polarizer, PC—pockels cell, CAM—camera, CEM—cavity end mirror, PP—pulse picker, MM—motorized mirror mount.

FIG. 2. Control system logic scheme of the active alignment system. CAM—camera, MM—motorized mirror mount, IPC—industrial PC, CSS—cavity stabilization system, BSS—beam stabilization system, PLC—programmable logic controller, HMI—human machine interface.

and is divided into products for camera integration and a library with a variety of image processing algorithms. The camera operates at a frame rate of 10 fps. Captured images from the camera undergo background image subtraction, followed by the application of a Region of Interest (ROI) to reduce the area of focus instead of processing data from the entire camera frame. Thresholding is then applied, where pixel values are set to zero if their intensity is below the threshold level. Afterward, the centroid for both axes is calculated. The centroid values from all cameras are transmitted to the second independent PLC. The image is subsequently processed by applying a color map, an overlay, resizing it, and then displaying it to the user. The second PLC uses the calculated centroid values as input for the PID controllers in the CSS and BSS alignment systems to determine the control action for each actuator.

The implemented control system uses a classical feedback loop to maintain the desired centroid position $w(t)$ of the laser beam. The system calculates the error $e(t)$ as

$$e(t) = w(t) - y(t), \quad (1)$$

where $y(t)$ is the calculated centroid position detected by the system. The control action is defined in two stages. The regulator computes the required control action $u_f(t)$, representing the number of steps the piezo actuator must take to correct the error,

$$u_f(t) = r_0 \cdot e(t), \quad (2)$$

where r_0 is the proportional gain of the regulator. The final control action $u(t)$ is then calculated by adding an offset u_0 , which represents the current position of the piezo motor:

$$u(t) = u_f(t) + u_0. \quad (3)$$

To improve system robustness and avoid unnecessary regulation, several constraints and conditions are applied. Regulation

is triggered only when the absolute value of the error exceeds a predefined threshold T_{thr} :

$$|e(t)| > T_{thr}. \quad (4)$$

This ensures that minor fluctuations, potentially caused by noise or minor miscalculations, do not activate the control loop. The regulation continues until the error is reduced below half the threshold value,

$$|e(t)| \leq \frac{T_{thr}}{2}. \quad (5)$$

This hysteresis mechanism avoids oscillatory behavior around the threshold and stabilizes the control process. The reliability of centroid detection is ensured by monitoring the total pixel intensity I_{total} of the detection camera. Regulation is disabled under the following conditions:

If $I_{total} < I_{min}$, the beam is assumed to be missing from the camera's field of view, likely due to misalignment.

If $I_{total} > I_{max}$, the camera is considered saturated, leading to unreliable centroid calculations.

In both cases, the system halts regulation and alerts the operator to prevent corrections based on erroneous data. These measures prevent the regulator from reacting to minor disturbances or invalid centroid data caused by beam misalignment, noise, or saturation effects, ensuring consistent performance.

III. ACTUATOR PROPERTIES

The correction of the alignment and pointing of the laser beam is made by four mirrors that can be actuated with Picomotor™ actuators. Each motorized mirror mount allows for rotation around the pitch and yaw axes. The Picomotor is equipped with a piezoelectric transducer and uses the difference between dynamic and static friction to rotate a precision 80-pitch screw. The frequency of the motion steps is limited to 2 kHz, but very high resolution (less than 30 nm per step) and set-and-forget stability make the Picomotor very useful for precise alignment. The main disadvantage to use piezoelectric actuator (PEA) is the nonlinear hysteresis effect that causes positioning errors, which critically limit the precision of PEAs.⁷

In the context of piezo actuators, it is necessary to discuss the possibility of simplifying the complex dynamics of these actuators by considering only their static behavior. Given the measurement interval of 100 ms (10 Hz), the dynamic response of the Picomotors is not detectable within this timeframe. The Picomotors' response time is much faster than the sampling period, meaning any dynamic behavior occurs and settles within each sampling interval, rendering it effectively unobservable at this measurement frequency. Therefore, for the purposes of our control system and given the measurement period, we can accurately model the behavior of the Picomotors using a static relationship.

This simplification is consistent with the principles of Tikhonov's theorem, which justifies the use of a quasi-static model when the fast subsystem—in this case, the Picomotors—exhibits exponential stability. Tikhonov's theorem ensures that, under such conditions, the dynamic response can be approximated by a static model without significant loss of accuracy, provided that the fast

dynamics settle within the sampling period, as our measurements confirm.

The simplification significantly reduces the complexity of the control algorithm and computational requirements without compromising the accuracy or performance of the system. This approach assumes that within each 100 ms interval, the Picomotor reaches its final position for any given input change, thus allowing us to treat the actuator's output as if it were instantaneously reaching a steady state. Consequently, the control system can be designed and tuned based on this static assumption, ensuring robust and reliable operation while maintaining precise control over the laser alignment.

For control design, a description of the characteristics of individual control elements and, generally, for system description, the static characteristics and static gain are used. Static characteristics represent the relationship between the output variable $y(t)$ in steady state and the input variable $u(t)$ in steady state,

$$u = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} u(t) \quad y = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} y(t). \quad (6)$$

In our case, the input variable $u(t)$ is the number of steps of the picomotor actuator. For measuring output variable $y(t)$, we use a camera (Allied Vision Manta G-201) equipped with a Sony ICX274 sensor with a pixel size of $4.4 \times 4.4 \mu\text{m}^2$. The output variable is then the angle in mrad calculated from the beam centroid movement on the camera sensor in pixels.

If the static characteristics are not a straight line and do not pass through the origin, it is a nonlinear element. Figure 3(a) shows the effect of the Picomotor Piezo Mirror Mount (Newport 8807) placed 270 mm in front of the camera on a test bench. The step change of the input variable was 200 steps with a 2 kHz step frequency, and after each movement was finished, an average of multiple beam centroid calculations was performed to get a stable output variable. The system clearly exhibits gain $K1$ with increasing control inputs and gain $K2$, which is greater with decreasing inputs. This implies that

FIG. 3. Static characteristics of the Picomotor mirror mount placed 270 mm in front of the camera. (a) without compensation (b) with the linearization method applied.

the system is nonlinear and cannot be described by a single transfer function across the entire input spectrum. To deal with such a nonlinear system, which decrease the precision of the active alignment, we use a simple but effective linearization tool.

Static characteristics in Fig. 3(a) consist of two linear segments. The condition of linearity is not met because the line does not pass through the origin during the reverse movement. After performing linear regression on the measured data in Fig. 3(a), we obtain the equation of the line for the forward movement $y_1 = 0.0007u$, and for the reverse movement the equation $y_2 = 0.0008u - 1.9546$. The slope of the line for the forward movement y_1 is 13% smaller than the slope of the line for the reverse movement. If we reduce the backward step by this proportion, we should achieve linearization of the static characteristic. However, it is not possible to reduce the step size for the picomotor. The step size is determined by the shape of the control voltage curve, and with the Newport 8703 driver used, the pulse shape cannot be altered. Therefore, the linearization was performed via software. The linearization process was implemented by defining a variable within the function block, which adjusts the motor position control output based on a cumulative sum. For each movement step, the sum is incremented, and when it exceeds one threshold, the motor position is updated without generating a voltage pulse to the picomotor. Conversely, if the sum falls below another threshold, a pulse is added without changing the motor position. This method compensates for differences between forward and reverse step sizes by either skipping or adding pulses where necessary. The linearization results are presented in Fig. 3(b).

This technique is very useful because it allows the application of linear control methods to nonlinear systems, significantly simplifying the analysis and design of controllers. More precisely, linearization enables the use of classical techniques, such as PID control, which are well-developed and widely used in the field of automation and control.

This procedure removes the critical limitation of PEAs precision and allows us to use standard procedures for control design around the operating point of the actuator.

A very important motion parameter in general is speed. In the case of the Picomotor actuator, the speed is changed by adjusting the frequency of the motion steps. However, changing the frequency of the steps alters the static gain and, therefore, affects the linearization. Figure 4 illustrates static characteristics of the mirror mount with the effect of decreasing the frequency of the Picomotor actuator to 1 kHz. The angular resolution of the mirror mount increased

FIG. 4. Static characteristics of Picomotor mirror mount with a limited step frequency of 1 kHz in comparison to a 2 kHz step frequency.

with the decreasing frequency, so the maximum number of steps had to be limited to 15 000 steps to avoid exceeding the size of the camera chip. The system in Fig. 4 presents gain K1 with increasing control inputs and gain K2, which is smaller with decreasing inputs. Therefore, the change in gain must be considered when adjusting the motor speed in order to successfully increase the precision of the PEAs.

IV. TEST MEASUREMENTS AND RESULTS

The laser system configuration used for the test measurements is described and presented in Fig. 1. To measure the beam position jitter and power stability, the power was measured by a thermal sensor (Ophir F150A-BB-26), and beam position was monitored with the camera detectors, the stabilization system being not active. The results in Fig. 5(a) reveal the pointing instability of the cavity during the first 70 min of the laser run, resulting in power instability and decreasing output power of the regenerative amplifier, which required multiple manual realignments of the cavity mirrors during the measurement (marked with red lines). The power stability for the first 20 min of the measurement was calculated to be 1.87% RMS and 7.43% pk-pk.

The main reason for the decrease in amplifier output power can be visibly demonstrated in the image of the pump spot monitored by CAM1 in Fig. 6. In this image, the position of the cavity mode on the disk is shifted from the center of the pump spot, which is the ideal position for the optimal function of the cavity. The image on the left is a raw image taken by the camera. The image on the right is a processed image, which is the result of the raw image subtracted from the calibration image and with an applied color map.

Implementing the active cavity stabilization system (CSS), the positional errors on both cameras, CAM1 and CAM2, are significantly reduced, as seen in Fig. 7. For quantifying the increase in

FIG. 5. Power stability, the stabilization system being inactive (a), where manual adjustments of the cavity mirrors are marked with red lines. Power stability when the control system automatically aligns the cavity mirrors using CSS (b).

FIG. 6. Shifted position of the cavity mode on the disk from the optimal position in the center of the pump spot.

FIG. 7. Stability of cavity mode position monitored by CAM1, the stabilization system being inactive (a) and automatically aligned using CSS (b). Positional stability measured by CAM2, the CSS inactive (c) and CSS active (d).

stability, the beam positional stability $\Delta_x(z')$ and $\Delta_y(z')$ was calculated according to ISO 11145:2018,⁸ as presented in Table I. Beam positional stability is determined as four times the standard deviation of the measured beam positional movement in the z' plane. Increased positional stability resulted in increased output power stability [shown in Fig. 5(b)], with the power stability improving to

TABLE I. Beam positional stability $\Delta_x(z')$, $\Delta_y(z')$ on CAM1 and CAM2, stabilization not active and using CSS.

		No. stabilization	CSS active
CAM1	$\Delta_x(z')$ (μm)	54.3	6.7
	$\Delta_y(z')$ (μm)	6.8	5.9
CAM2	$\Delta_x(z')$ (μm)	71.2	25.7
	$\Delta_y(z')$ (μm)	328.3	49.1

0.99% RMS and 4.4% pk-pk, and no longer requiring manual readjustments of the cavity mirrors. However, even though the power and positional stability of the cavity are secured, pointing instability at the input of the compressor occurs, as illustrated in Figs. 8(b) and 8(d).

When both the cavity stabilization system (CSS) and the beam stabilization system (BSS) are employed, the residual positional error on the nearfield and far-field cameras (CAM3 and CAM4) is significantly reduced, as depicted in Figs. 8(b)–8(e). The integration of both stabilization systems demonstrates a synergistic effect, greatly enhancing the overall stability and performance of the laser system. As a result, the power stability further improves to 0.79% RMS and 3.88% pk-pk, as shown in Fig. 8(a). The increase in the beam positional stability is shown in Table II.

FIG. 8. Power stability, both stabilizations—CSS and BSS being active (a). Positional stability measured by CAM3 (b) and CAM4 (d) using only CSS. Positional stability measured by CAM3 (c) and CAM4 (e) using both CSS and BSS.

TABLE II. Beam positional stability $\Delta_x(z')$, $\Delta_y(z')$ on CAM3 and CAM4, using only CSS and both CSS and BSS active.

		Only CSS	CSS and BSS
CAM3	$\Delta_x(z')$ (μm)	43.3	20.8
	$\Delta_y(z')$ (μm)	115.4	18.9
CAM4	$\Delta_x(z')$ (μm)	62.5	15.4
	$\Delta_y(z')$ (μm)	19.1	19.7

The control system is capable of compensating for long-term variations due to thermal expansion of optical elements, optical benches, and their supporting structures, which arise from environmental temperature changes. However, sampling with a period of 100 ms is not able to detect rapid changes caused by, for example, vibrations of optical elements and benches. This may be the reason for the remaining instabilities in Figs. 7(b), 7(d), 8(c), and 8(e).

The near-field and far-field measurements indicate that the beam is consistently maintained at the desired positions, leading to a highly stable output beam with minimal fluctuations. This dual stabilization approach not only mitigates the residual pointing errors but also ensures that the laser system operates at its peak efficiency, providing reliable and consistent performance over extended periods.

V. CONCLUSION

We have developed a stabilization control system for thin-disk platform lasers and demonstrated its operation. The system is based on the automatic alignment of four motorized mirrors. The non-linear hysteresis effect of these piezo-actuated mirrors is reduced by the linearization method to increase the actuator precision. The control system optimizes the position of the cavity mode on the thin disk, which leads to increased output power stability. Additionally, to reduce pointing error at the input of the compressor, the stabilization system aligns the beam on near-field and far-field cameras. Overall, the control system ensures robust and maintenance-free operation of the laser throughout the day, which is necessary for the use of the laser in industrial applications.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

J. Horáček: Conceptualization (lead). **L. Hubka:** Supervision (equal). **M. Chyla:** Conceptualization (supporting). **T. Mocek:** Project administration (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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